

Enabling Smeagol on Xeon Phi: Lessons Learned

Alin M Elena^{a*} and Ivan Rungger^b

^a*Irish Centre for High-End Computing, Dublin 2, Ireland*

^b*School of Physics and CRANN, Trinity College, Dublin 2, Ireland*

Abstract: The aim of the work is to port the quantum electron transport code Smeagol to the Intel Xeon Phi (MIC) based hybrid architecture. Smeagol is based on density functional theory, and utilises the non-equilibrium Green's function formalism (NEGF) to calculate the charge density at an applied bias voltage. We successfully ported Smeagol to run in native mode on the MIC, however for small systems the run-time on the host is always significantly shorter than the one on the MIC. It is not possible to run large systems on a single MIC due to memory limits. For large systems we adopt a different strategy for efficiently using this hybrid architecture: we propose to run most of the calculation on a number of host processors, distributed over a set of nodes, using MPI, and to port only the most time-consuming operations to the MIC for each host. This allows us to take advantage of the large memory on the host, which enables calculations for large systems. We show that in Smeagol the most time-consuming operation is the inversion required to obtain the Green's function within the NEGF formalism. Our results indicate that for sufficiently large systems our implementation of the recursive Green's functions (RGF) inversion algorithm can indeed run faster on the MIC plus host setup than on the host. This is also true for the whole Smeagol code utilised in such an offload mode.

1 Introduction

The aim of this paper is to present initial findings of our porting of the *ab initio* electron transport code Smeagol, [1], [2] to the new Intel Xeon Phi based computer architecture. Smeagol allows for the calculation of the quantum electron transport properties of nano-devices at an applied bias voltage from first principles. In order to obtain the electron density in such systems out of equilibrium at an applied voltage the non-equilibrium Green's function formalism (NEGF) is used, and the Hamiltonian is obtained from the density functional theory (DFT) localised orbitals basis set code SIESTA, see Ref. [3]. Smeagol is used to predict current versus voltage characteristics across different types of nano-devices, such as molecular junctions, thin films, nanowires and two-dimensional materials such as graphene. Such theoretical calculations are important in order to rationalise the multitude of experimental data on transport characteristics of such junctions for both fundamental scientific understanding as well as for design of new devices. An example of a successful application of these methods are magnetic tunnel junctions, where NEGF-based first principle calculations have driven experimental research, and which are used routinely in hard disk drives read heads and in magnetic random access memories. Since Smeagol is a first principles code no free parameters are needed, so that the code has quantitative predictive capabilities. The current versus voltage characteristics of such nano-devices are however only one of the outputs, since the code allows the calculation of all the electronic structure properties obtained also with standard DFT codes, with the main difference that these can be evaluated also out of equilibrium at an applied bias potential. Moreover it also allows for structural relaxations and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations at an applied voltage, which can give significantly different results from calculations at equilibrium conditions.

*Corresponding author. *E-mail address:* alin.elena@ichec.ie

An example of an important practical application for quantum transport in nano-meter-scale devices, where Smeagol is widely used to calculate the properties, are magnetoresistive devices based on the giant magnetoresistance (GMR) and tunnelling magnetoresistance (TMR). These form the key component in many devices, such as magnetic read heads in hard disk drives and magnetic random access memories. While MgO based TMR devices, pioneered by the NEGF based theoretical work of W. Butler and collaborators, Ref. [4], are well established, the quest for new junction stacks with improved performance and stability is ongoing, especially with respect to the ability to switch the magnetisation direction through an applied current without damaging the junction stack. The DFT based Smeagol electron transport code can tackle these questions from a theoretical point of view, and has indeed already been widely used in the past to study such systems. More recently quasi two-dimensional (2D) materials have emerged as a class of materials with huge potential for nanoelectronics applications. In order to understand their electron transport properties, and with them the device performance, first principles electron transport simulations are essential. On the more fundamental aspect electron transport simulations are also an essential tool in order to describe many different scanning tunnelling microscope (STM) experiments through nano-objects.

The typical device setup consists of two metallic electrodes, separated by a spacer, which can for example be a molecule or a thin film. Inherently the simulations of such nano-device setups involve rather large supercells, and Smeagol can currently treat systems with more than 10000 atoms. Moreover, since experimentally such nano-junctions show considerable fluctuations in their structures, which are then reflected in the conductivities, one needs to perform many calculations for different realistic interfaces in order to obtain statistically relevant results that can be compared to experimental data. Such calculations therefore require considerable computational resources, and therefore efficient parallelisation of the code is of paramount importance. Smeagol scales well in parallel on standard compute clusters, and on BlueGeneQ systems scaling has been demonstrated on up to more than 10000 processors for calculations at an applied voltage. The Intel MIC architecture is an emerging technology that can provide the possibility to "accelerate" sections of parallel code at a reduced cost and power consumption. We therefore aim to port the Smeagol code to the Intel MIC and to compare the performance to other available computer architectures, such as standard compute clusters or BlueGeneQ systems.

2 Smeagol Performance

Smeagol uses a combination of MPI and OpenMP for parallelisation. Within Smeagol the electron density is calculated using a self-consistent cycle. At each iteration the calculation consists of two main parts. First the DFT Hamiltonian matrix is calculated using the input charge density within the SIESTA part of the code, where sets of rows of the Hamiltonian matrix are calculated on different MPI tasks. Since this involves little communication between processors, and an efficient parallel Fast Fourier Transform is used to obtain the electrostatic potential, the overall parallel efficiency of this first stage is good. The second stage is the calculation of the output electron density within the NEGF formalism. This second stage is computationally much more demanding than the first one, especially at applied bias voltage, and therefore the overall scaling of the code is determined by the scaling of this part. Within the NEGF the electron density is obtained by performing an energy integral over the lesser Green's function, which is itself based on the retarded Green's function matrix (GFM) of the system. The energy integral is evaluated as a sum over energy points, and at each energy point the GFM is calculated. The NEGF implementation in Smeagol supports two levels of MPI parallelism: a) k-points, b) energy points, and one level of OpenMP parallelism over atomic orbitals within the calculation of the GFM. Moreover, for the calculations of current vs. voltage curves, all bias points can be submitted concurrently, giving an additional level of coarse-grained parallelism.

We first evaluate the Smeagol code on a single MIC by using an intermediate size test system. We note here the memory constraint of 8 GiB per MIC limits the system size if only one MIC is used. For larger systems the code needs to be run on multiple MICs to increase total available memory. We choose Al-FDCA-Al (FDCA is

Figure 1: Ball and stick representation of the Al-FDCA-Al system. Al, Fe, C, O and H atoms are coloured as blue, ochre, cyan, red and white. FDCA is atomically attached to the Al(111) surface. The total number of atoms in the system 133.

1,1'-Ferrocene Dicarboxylic Acid) as test system (Fig. 1), for which the electronic transport properties were studied using Smeagol in Ref. [5]. The parameters for the simulations are a voltage of 0.2 V, for which we use 64 energy points in the imaginary plane, and also 64 energy points on the real energy axis. The mesh cutoff is 100 Ry and we use 6 k-points. The low mesh cutoff is necessary to enable the code to run on a single MIC.

Porting the code to run on Xeon Phi involved an update of the building system. Initial versions of the Intel compilers had bugs that caused the code to give incorrect results. All these bugs were reported to Intel (DPD200247222, DPD200246949, DPD200247006, DPD200247866). After these compiler bugs were fixed in new released versions of the compiler, Smeagol runs on the MIC giving the same results as on the host processors. We run the code using the system chosen above in 3 different modes: MPI on one card, MPI on multiple cards and MPI symmetric (the MPI universe consists of processes on both Xeon Phi cards and the host).

Figure 2: MPI scaling with one OpenMP thread. Maximum number of 32 MPI processes is due to limitations in the memory available on MIC.

Initial tests were run with 32 pure MPI processes on a Xeon Phi card (mic0), where the results are presented in Fig. 2. We measured the time needed to solve a typical SCF cycle (SCF in Fig. 2), along with time to solve the electronic transport problem only (EM in Fig. 2). EM is split into two main parts: time to interface with SIESTA (interface in Fig. 2), and effective time of computation for NEGF (NEGF in Fig. 2). We can easily see that the longest amount of time spent is on computing the NEGF, where the factor 6 is to account for each k-point that is

solved. One can note that the efficiency is not ideal but for 32 processes is still above 80%.

We next focused on the hybrid runs. We have selected the case of 4 and 32 MPI processes and for each of them we added OpenMP threads until the card was full (240 threads, see Fig. 3). As the time spent in the interface part of the code is constant we omitted it from the results presented here. Both cases show a poor scalability with the increase in OpenMP threads for all the times of interest to us. As we will show in the next sections, this is mainly due to the small system size used for this test system. The next two sections provide more detail on scalability for both MPI and OpenMP for different system sizes.

Figure 3: OpenMP scaling curves for Smeagol when using 4 MPI processes, left and 32 mpi processes, right. The maximum number of threads is limited by 240 threads available on MIC and *balanced* affinity.

3 MPI Performance

In order to understand the MPI performance we investigated how the running times change when we distribute the processes on different cards/hosts (see Fig. 4). We consider two cases: running with 32 MPI processes and running with 64 MPI processes. For 32 MPI processes the tasks are distributed equally across two Xeon Phi cards (mic0 and mic1, 16 MPI processes for each card). The CPU only case (h1+h2 in the above mentioned figure, consists of two hosts) is 12 times faster than running only on mic0 on two separate hosts (h1-mic0+h2-mic0 in Fig. 4). The difference in speed between CPU and MIC can largely be explained by the difference in speed of the processors on MIC and host. However, a significant part has to come also from the MPI communication. Using the mic0 cards on two different hosts to distribute the MPI processes the time spent in the interface part of the code increases by a factor of 2.5 compared with the case when the MPI processes are distributed on a single mic0. Running 64 MPI processes in a symmetric way, 20 on host and 22 on each MIC results in faster time than using only the MICs but still inferior to the case of 32 MPI processes only on hosts by a factor of seven in the case of NEGF.

We have assessed the MPI performance by performing bandwidth measurements in our MPI topology, see Fig. 5. The picture that emerges is that of a highly heterogeneous network structure between the hosts and Xeon Phis. For mic0 and mic1 on the same host communication is three times slower than the communication between mic0 and mic0 on different hosts. A further reduction by a factor of 2 in communication performance is seen when mic0 and mic1 are on different hosts. Furthermore when we try to communicate between two mic1 cards on different hosts a further reduction by 2 in performance is observed. Communication within a single MIC however is significantly faster. This situation can be explained if we have in mind the fact that each MIC is associated in our setup with a CPU socket and mic0 and the infiniband network adaptor are on the same socket. Each time when we try to engage mic1 in MPI communication a more complex network structure is involved as the communication happens over the QPI channel in between the two sockets on the same processor. Another point to note is that intra-mic communication is limited by the memory bandwidth, hence the factor of 2 difference in bandwidth when we measure it between two MPI processes on the same mic0 and on different mic0 or mic1 in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: MPI performance for Smeagol when running on pure MPI processes distributed inter-nodes, inter-mics and combinations. The entries prefixed with 64- run on 64 MPI processes the rest on 32 MPI processes. h1 and h2 stand for processes one and two involved in the MPI communication. h1-mic0 stands for the first Xeon Phi card attached to host one, h1-mic1 is the second card attached to h1 and similarly for h2. All the processes were equally distributed between hosts and cards involved with the exception of 64-h1+h1-mic0+h1-mic1 which had 20 MPI processes on host and 22 on each card. The measurements were performed on the FIONN cluster at ICHEC

All the measurements presented in this section were performed on the Xeon Phi partition of FIONN cluster at ICHEC, similar results were obtained using EURORA system at CINECA.

Figure 5: Bandwidth between host and MICs. Using Intel MPI Benchmark Ping Pong. (I_MPI_DAPL_PROVIDER_LIST=ofa-v2-mlx4_0-1u,ofa-v2-scif0,ofa-v2-mcm-1;I_MPI_FABRICS=shm:dapl). Data obtained on FIONN-cluster at ICHEC, very similar numbers were obtained on EURORA at CINECA.

4 Shared Memory Performance

In this section we address the threading performance of the MIC for different problem sizes and therefore matrix sizes on the Xeon Phi. The main time within the NEGF kernel is spent for the inversion of a block tridiagonal matrix, M , defined as

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} A_1 & B_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_1 & A_2 & B_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & C_2 & A_3 & B_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_3 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots & \ddots & B_{N-2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{N-2} & A_{N-1} & B_{N-1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{N-1} & A_N \end{bmatrix}$$

We are interested in computing the inverse, M^{-1} . Each block, A_i , is square of dimensions $n_i \times n_i$, the off-diagonal blocks B_i are of dimensions $n_i \times n_{i+1}$ and C_i are of dimensions $n_{i+1} \times n_i$, respectively. In addition, the blocks are sparse. The algorithm to compute the inverse of matrix, M , consists of matrix additions, multiplications and inversions of these blocks. In Smeagol we use a custom made implementation of the Recursive Green's function (RGF) algorithm to invert this tridiagonal matrix, see Refs. [6] and [7], where we do not need to compute the whole inverse but only the part corresponding to the original tridiagonal pattern plus the first and last block columns. Within Smeagol the sizes of the blocks for systems currently calculated vary between $10^2 \times 10^2$ to $10^4 \times 10^4$. We therefore analyse the timings for the inversion for matrix sizes in this range. The block size in Smeagol is highly dependent on the geometry of the physical system considered. For the small test system considered in Section 2

the matrix sizes are on the lower limit of the range, namely about 150×150 .

We start by investigating the performance of ZGEMM/ZGETRF and ZGETRI, the BLAS/LAPACK routines that are used to perform large part of the operations in the Smeagol RGF inversion algorithm. The results are presented in Fig. 6. The overall performance in terms of GFlop/s for all three operations is good, with a peak performance achieved for the largest matrices for ZGEMM of 840 GFlop/s and 730 GFlop/s for ZGETRF and 400 GFlop/s for ZGETRI on the Xeon Phi. For all these routines the performance on the Xeon Phi is better than the performance on the host by a factor of 2. It should be pointed out that large variations are observed on Intel Xeon Phi depending on the thread affinity we use, with *compact* and *balanced* offering the best performance, and with *scatter* offering the worst. The situation is reversed in the case of the host where the best performance is offered by *scatter* and worst by *compact*. It can also be seen that while the peak performance in the case of ZGEMM is reached for relatively small orders of the matrices involved in the multiplication, at dimensions of 500 by 500 the Xeon Phi already achieves 500 GFlop/s. However, this is not the case for ZGETRF and ZGETRI. In particular in the range up to $N=10000$ the MICs do not show higher performance than the host. For these sizes, ZGETRI shows worse performance on the MIC for these sizes than the host.

Figure 6: Average performance of different linear algebra routines from MKL (version 11.1.0) on host Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2660 v2 @ 2.20GHz with 20 openMP threads and on MIC Xeon Phi 5110P with 240 openMP threads. (Running on MIC case for *compact* and *balanced* affinities gives curves on top of each other.) a) The Xeon Phi ZGEMM multiplying square matrices of size N, b) ZGETRF and c) ZGETRI parts of the complex matrix inversion of size N

The scaling over the OpenMP threads for ZGEMM/ZGETRF and ZGETRI for matrices of sizes of interest is presented in Fig. 7. The ZGEMM routine shows good scaling for $N \geq 1000$ (where N is the order of the matrix) and reasonably good scaling for smaller sizes however, the inversion routines ZGETRF/ZGETRI do not perform well. We therefore conclude that the LU decomposition and the last step of the inversion are the real bottlenecks in our inversion algorithm. In particular, for a large number of threads ZGETRI shows an increase of time when the thread number is increased, which clearly degrades the performance for the inversion of matrices on the MIC. We also note that the curves are not smooth, but rather that performance is better for some particular number of

threads. For example, for ZGETRF it is good for 16 threads, but poor for 4, 8, 32 and 64 threads.

The analysis of the performance of ZGETRF/ZGETRI explains why for the small test system threading performance is poor, since for small block matrices of the order of 150 those operations do not scale well for an increasing number of threads.

Figure 7: Scaling curves on Xeon Phi for ZGEMM/ZGETRF/ZGETRI for sizes of the matrices common during production runs of Smeagol. The number of threads used was 1,2,4,8,16,32,120,240 and thread affinity was *balanced*.

We conclude this section by looking at the overall performance of the whole RGF algorithm. The algorithm uses a mixture of sparse and dense matrix operations. For dense matrices we use the BLAS/LAPACK routines discussed above. We implemented a test code that generates random matrices with a given number of blocks of different sizes and filling factors. This allows us to simulate the matrices generated during a Smeagol calculation. Here we consider two matrices M , each made up of 5 blocks, where the block size is set to $N_{block} = 2000$ for one matrix and $N_{block} = 4000$ for the other. For each block we varied the sparsity, f , from 0.1% to 10% for the small matrix and to 1% and 4% for the big one. These are filling factors expected in a Smeagol calculation for large systems. The results are presented in Fig. 8. The inversion on Xeon Phi is slower than on the host for a low number of threads. However, when increasing the number of threads to the maximum value on the MIC and host, the required walltimes for cpu and MIC become similar. This is consistent with the ZGETRI/ZGETRF performance presented in the previous section, which is similar for matrix sizes between 2000 and 4000. Clearly the bigger the blocks in the calculation, the better the performance on the MIC. The threading performance on the host is good, at more than 50% for 20 threads, and also on the MIC it is drastically improved compared to the small matrix sizes of the test system in Section 2. In fact, for large filling it is above 50% for more than 100 threads, and is about 30% for 240 threads.

These results show that the MIC can potentially speed up Smeagol calculations for very large systems, where block sizes above 5000×5000 are to be expected. We therefore propose to carry out the large part of a Smeagol calculation in parallel on a number of hosts (e.g. 64 hosts), taking advantage of the large memory available, and to then perform the RGF algorithm on the MIC for increased performance in this key part of the code. However due to the memory limitations on the current version of MICs the whole RGF inversion algorithm will exceed the memory limits on the MICs for very large systems. We have therefore started to implement a version of the RGF algorithm, where instead of moving the large block matrices to the MIC all at the same time, we asynchronously move them between MIC and host at the required point in the algorithm. In this way we can overcome the memory limitations while at the same time preserving the performance of the MIC for large matrices.

Figure 8: Scaling curves for our inverter for sizes of the matrices common during production runs of big systems. We considered 5 blocks for the diagonal, each block with a size N_{block} of either 2000 or 4000, so that the total matrix size N is between 10000 and 20000, with varying degrees of sparsity from 0.1% to 10%. The number of threads used were 1,2,4,8,16,32,120,236 for the MIC and 1,2,4,8,10,16,20 for the host.

5 Overlapping calculation Host - Xeon Phi

As discussed in the previous section, one way to address the issue of the limited memory on the Xeon Phi for calculations is to use it in offload mode, where only the block matrices required for a particular part in the RGF algorithm are offloaded to the MIC at that time. Since this is still work in progress, here we present some simplified results based on inversions of individual blocks. This step is actually required in the last part of the RGF algorithm,

where N_{blocks} dense matrices need to be inverted independently. We perform these independent inversions of blocks by using ZGETRF and ZGETRI. This part of the code can be easily parallelised using task parallelism. Let us consider the original pattern.

```
1 do i=1,N_blocks
2   invert(A(i))
3 end do
```

which we subsequently transform to:

```
1 !dir$ begin offload target(mic:myMic)
2 !dir$ copy data in
3 !dir$ signal(s)
4 !$omp parallel
5 !$omp single
6 do i=1,p_mic
7   !$omp task
8   invert(A(i))
9   !$omp end task
10 end do
11 !$omp end single nowait
12 !$omp end parallel
13 !dir$ end offload
14 do j=p_mic+1,N_blocks
15   invert(A(j))
16 end do
17 !dir$ offload_wait target(mic:myMic) wait(s)
```

In the transformed algorithm above the initial number of matrices N_{blocks} is divided into p_{mic} and $N_{blocks} - p_{mic}$. We transfer the first p_{mic} matrices to Xeon Phi and using OpenMP task parallelism we invert all of them in parallel. At the same time we invert the remainder of blocks on the CPU.

We have implemented this scheme and we have found that for relatively small values of N_{blocks} ($N_{blocks} = 9$) we already reduce the inversion time to half using only one Xeon Phi card (see Table 1), from ≈ 36 s that it takes to invert all the blocks using only the host to ≈ 18 s using one Xeon Phi card and the host. In our test we consider matrices of order $N_{block} = 2000$ and we use one thread on the host and 4 threads for each task on the Xeon Phi. For $p_{mic} = 5$ the Xeon Phi and CPU calculations overlapped almost perfectly when the affinity was set to *balanced*. Table 1 shows the results for *scatter*, *compact* and *balanced* affinities on the Xeon Phi. The first row lists the time the host needs to invert 4 blocks. The second row lists the time needed for Xeon Phi to invert 5 blocks. The fastest time is obtained for *balanced* affinity. The third row shows the time the CPU has to wait for the Xeon Phi to finish its inversion stage. The last row includes the CPU calculation time, overhead associated with transferring data from the Xeon Phi and wait time for the calculation. In all cases the host plus Xeon Phi setup provides almost a factor of 2 speedup relative to running on the host only. The refactored algorithm that we implemented here should perform better for larger physical systems with a larger number of blocks, where indeed p_{mic} can be much larger. In our tests we limited the number of threads to 4 on the Xeon Phi due to the relatively small matrix size and poor scaling of ZGETRF and ZGETRI (see Fig. 7). Although the full RGF algorithm has not been yet rewritten in such an offload mode, the results show that such an implementation can lead to good performance.

times	<i>compact</i>	<i>balanced</i>	<i>scatter</i>
compute cpu time	16.60	16.60	16.60
MIC time	20.31	16.54	19.27
CPU wait time	3.86	0.107	2.85
cpu time	21.72	17.92	20.68

Table 1: Results for overlapped inversion of 9 matrices 5 on Xeon Phi and 4 on host for different threads affinities. All the times are in seconds and a positive waiting time means the CPU waited for the Xeon Phi to finish. For *balanced* affinity where the waiting time is close to zero indicating an almost perfect overlap between the calculations. The overall speedup for the calculation for the Xeon Phi plus host setup is a factor of 2 compared with the CPU only calculation.

6 Conclusions

We have successfully ported Smeagol to run on the new Intel Xeon Phi architecture, and checked that the final results are the same as on a "typical" calculation on the host processors. "Normal" Smeagol calculations for small systems run on the MIC in native mode, but calculations for such small systems performed on the host processors are faster. This is simply because the calculations on the host CPUs are about one order of magnitude faster than on the MIC. Moreover the 8 GiB memory constraint on the MIC, limits system sizes for runs in native mode on a single MIC. The host and mic-mic MPI communications are found to be slow. A large amount of very small systems can be run in a "task-farming" mode as part of high-throughput calculations on the MICs, where we can take advantage of the large number of CPUs on the MIC. Given that the performance of Smeagol is largely determined by the performance of the subroutines used for matrix inversions, we can use the performance of these subroutines to evaluate the whole Smeagol performance. We evaluated the performance of the RGF algorithm on MIC and host, and found that for large block matrix sizes the MIC can be as fast as the host. Although with the current generation of MICs the performance of a single MIC can not be significantly higher than for the host, this is expected to improve with future MIC generations. In order to efficiently utilise the MIC and host for our algorithm we therefore suggest to run large part of the Smeagol calculation on the host, taking advantage of the large amount of memory available on the host, and to offload only the RGF inversion to the MIC, since this is the most time-consuming part. In order to avoid hitting the memory limit on the MIC during the RGF solver stage, the offload needs to be performed on a block-by-block basis rather than offloading all the blocks together. Within this project a preliminary implementation of such an offload algorithm has been implemented using asynchronous computation. Further work is needed to rewrite the whole RGF in such an offload mode which form part of our future development plans for Smeagol.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank ICHEC for access to the ICHEC's Xeon Phi partition on FIONN cluster, in particular Marco Grossi and Niall Wilson for their help in accessing it. We would also like to thank to Dr. Michael Lysaght for his critical reading of the manuscript. Part of the calculations were carried out on the EURORA system at CINECA.

This work was financially supported by the PRACE-IIP project funded in part by the EUs 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-261557.

References

- [1] A. R. Rocha, V. M. García-Suárez, S. Bailey, C. Lambert, J. Ferrer, and S. Sanvito, *Spin and molecular electronics in atomically generated orbital landscapes*, Phys. Rev. B, **73**, p. 085414, Feb 2006, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.73.085414. 1

-
- [2] I. Rungger and S. Sanvito, *Algorithm for the construction of self-energies for electronic transport calculations based on singularity elimination and singular value decomposition*, Phys. Rev. B, **78**, p. 035407, Jul 2008, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.78.035407. 1
- [3] J. M. Soler, E. Artacho, J. D. Gale, A. García, J. Junquera, P. Ordejón, and D. Sánchez-Portal, *The SIESTA method for ab initio order-N materials simulation*, Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter, **14**(11), p. 2745, 2002. 1
- [4] W. H. Butler, X.-G. Zhang, T. C. Schulthess, and J. M. MacLaren, *Spin-dependent tunneling conductance of Fe|MgO|Fe sandwiches*, Phys. Rev. B, **63**, p. 054416, Jan 2001, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevB.63.054416. 2
- [5] C. Morari, I. Rungger, A. R. Rocha, S. Sanvito, S. Melinte, and G.-M. Rignanesse, *Electronic transport properties of 1,1'-Ferrocene Dicarboxylic acid linked to Al(111) electrodes*, ACS Nano, **3**(12), p. 4137, 2009, doi: 10.1021/nm9012059. 3
- [6] I. N. Hajj and S. Skelboe, *A multilevel parallel solver for block tridiagonal and banded linear systems*, Parallel Computing, **15**(1–3), p. 21, 1990, ISSN 0167-8191, doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0167-8191\(90\)90029-9](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0167-8191(90)90029-9). 6
- [7] I. Rungger, *Assessment of embedding methods for order-N non-equilibrium transport calculations*, in preparation, 2014. 6